

THE ROLE OF GREEN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ENHANCING EMPLOYEE RESILIENCE AND ENGAGEMENT IN HYBRID WORK ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT :

The purpose of this study is to examine how Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) might enhance employee engagement and resilience in hybrid work contexts. The study examines how GHRM practices impact employee resilience using data from 86 IT workers in Coimbatore. It focuses on important engagement elements such as work-life balance, management support, job autonomy, and career advancement. The results show that GHRM practices and employee resilience are significantly positively correlated, with work-life balance having the greatest impact. To increase engagement and resilience, it is advised to support well-being initiatives, encourage teamwork, cultivate sustainability leadership, and recognize and promote sustainable employee behaviours.

KEYWORDS: Green Human Resource Management (GHRM), employee resilience, hybrid work, employee engagement, work-life balance, managerial support, job autonomy, sustainability, and career development.

INTRODUCTION :

Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) is an emerging approach that integrates environmental sustainability into traditional HR practices, focusing on creating eco-friendly work environments and promoting sustainable business operations. In recent years, the increasing shift towards hybrid work environments, where employees alternate between remote and onsite work, has introduced new challenges and opportunities in maintaining employee resilience and engagement. Employee resilience refers to the ability to adapt to change and overcome challenges, while engagement represents the emotional commitment employees have towards their work and organization.

In hybrid work settings, employees often face issues like work-life balance, lack of social interaction, and autonomy, making it critical for organizations to adopt practices that support both their well-being and engagement. GHRM practices, such as eco-friendly policies, sustainable development initiatives, and green leadership, offer a pathway to creating a supportive and resilient workforce. By aligning HR strategies with sustainability goals, organizations not only contribute to environmental responsibility but also foster a work culture that encourages flexibility, innovation, and employee well-being.

This study investigates the impact of GHRM practices on employee resilience and engagement in hybrid work environments, focusing on factors like managerial support, job autonomy, and career development, which are crucial for maintaining a motivated and resilient workforce.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

- In 2015 (Arulrajah, A., & Jermsittiparsert, K.) It explores the core concepts, principles, and practices of GHRM, and examines its potential impact on employee engagement. The study highlights how GHRM can contribute to a more sustainable and ethical work environment, leading to increased employee satisfaction and motivation.

- In **2017** (**Ansari, M. A., & Chauhan, P.**) proposed a conceptual framework linking GHRM practices to employee engagement. They argued that GHRM can foster a positive work environment, enhance employee satisfaction, and improve organizational performance.
- In **2020** (**Aboramadan, S.**) explored how GHRM practices can contribute to employee well-being. He found that GHRM can promote a healthy work environment, reduce stress, and improve job satisfaction.
- In **2021**(**Kim et al.**) examined the relationship between GHRM practices, employee engagement, and organizational performance in the hotel industry. They found that GHRM practices can positively impact employee engagement and, in turn, improve organizational performance.
- In **2022** (**Masuda and Tsuji**) conducted a systematic review of the literature on hybrid work arrangements and their impact on employee well-being. They found that hybrid work can have both positive and negative effects on employee well-being, depending on factors such as work-life balance, social interaction, and autonomy.
- In **2023** (**Xu and Liu's**) examine the relationship between Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) and organizational innovation. They explore how GHRM practices can foster a culture of innovation, encourage employee creativity, and promote sustainable business practices. The review highlights the potential synergies between GHRM and innovation in driving organizational success and sustainability.
- In **2023** (**Chen and Chen's**) explore the relationship between Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). They find that GHRM practices can positively impact CSR activities, and vice versa. The study highlights the potential synergies between these two areas, demonstrating how organizations can achieve both environmental and social goals through effective HR practices.

OBJECTIVES:

- To analyse the impact of GHRM practices on employee resilience in hybrid work environments.

- To examine the relationship between employee engagement levels and organisational support for sustainability initiatives.
- To identify the most common factors influencing employee engagement in a hybrid work environment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This is a descriptive study. Simple random sampling was used to select 86 IT employees in Coimbatore city.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS:

Primary and secondary sources provide a framework for the data collection for this research. The primary data refers to information gathered through a field survey for the first time. The data classified as secondary were previously collected by another party and subjected to statistical analysis.

SOURCES OF DATA:

- **PRIMARY DATA:**

Primary and secondary data provide a framework for the data gathering for this research. The primary data has been obtained from employees of various IT companies in Coimbatore, through structured questionnaires.

- **SECONDARY DATA:**

The secondary data has been obtained from published and unpublished literature on the topics and from books, journals, websites, magazines, etc. The data regarding the company profile industry profile are collected from official records and the internet

SAMPLE SIZE – 100

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

REGRESSION ANALYSIS :

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.271	1	.271	.153	.027 ^b
	Residual	149.461	84	1.779		
	Total	149.733	85			

a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE RESILIENCE

b. Predictors: (Constant), GHRM PRACTICES

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.568	.390		9.156	.000
	GHRM PRACTICES	.045	.114	.043	.391	.027

a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE RESILIENCE

INFERENCE - The above table has a significant impact or influence on **GHRM PRACTICES WITH EMPLOYEE RESILIENCE** because its significant level is less than 0.05 - 0.027.

FREQUENCY ANALYSIS :

FACTOR INFLUENCING EE

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	MANAGERIAL SUPPORT	22	25.3	25.6	25.6
	CAREER DEVELOPMENT	3	3.4	3.5	29.1
	WORKLIFE BALANCE	42	48.3	48.8	77.9
	JOB AUTONOMY	19	21.8	22.1	100.0
	Total	86	98.9	100.0	
Missing	System	1	1.1		
Total		87	100.0		

INFERENCE - In the above table, 42 respondents said **work-life balance** is the main factor which influences, 22 respondents said **Managerial Support**, 19 respondents said **Job Autonomy**, and 3 respondents said **Career Development**.

FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

FINDING FROM FREQUENCY ANALYSIS :

- 42 respondents selected **work-life balance** as the main influence factor.
- 22 respondents selected **Managerial Support** as the main influence factor.
- 19 respondents selected **Job autonomy** as the main influence factor.
- 3 respondents selected **Career Development** as the main influence factor.

FINDINGS FROM REGRESSION ANALYSIS :

- This study shows there is a significant impact or influence on **GHRM PRACTICES WITH EMPLOYEE RESILIENCE** because its significant level is less than 0.05 – 0.027.

SUGGESTION :

Organizations can enhance employee resilience and engagement in hybrid work environments by incorporating well-being programs focused on sustainability, fostering collaboration through virtual platforms, and promoting social interaction. A sustainability leadership program can drive GHRM initiatives and align them with organizational goals. Customizing GHRM practices for different employee segments ensures inclusivity, while recognizing and rewarding sustainable behaviors boosts morale. By prioritizing work-life balance, offering managerial support, and empowering employees with job autonomy, organizations can create a supportive culture. These strategies, combined with clear career development pathways, will foster a resilient, motivated, and engaged workforce.

CONCLUSION :

The results of this study show that employee resilience in hybrid work settings is significantly impacted by Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices. Regression analysis results demonstrate that GHRM practices have a beneficial impact on employee resilience, as evidenced by a significant level of 0.027, below the level of 0.05. According to this, including sustainable HR practices improves workers' capacity to adjust to and succeed in flexible, hybrid work environments while simultaneously advancing environmental goals. Furthermore, the frequency analysis shows that, in hybrid work settings, work-life balance is the most important element impacting employee engagement, followed by career growth, job autonomy, and management support. This suggests employees consider maintaining a healthy balance between their personal and professional lives to be important.

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